

Investigation of oxidative amine degradation on corrosion behavior of 304L and 316L stainless steels in MEA-based solutions

E. Lamprou¹, F. Stergioudi¹, A. Baxevani¹, N. Michailidis¹, E. Nessi², A.I. Papadopoulos², P. Seferlis³

¹Physical Metallurgy Laboratory, Mechanical Engineering Department, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, 54124 Thessaloniki, Greece

²Chemical Process and Energy Resources Institute, Centre for Research and Technology Hellas, 57001 Thessaloniki, Greece

³Laboratory of Machine Dynamics, Mechanical Engineering Department, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, 54124 Thessaloniki, Greece

Email for corresponding author: fstergio@meng.auth.gr

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1. Introduction

Oxidative degradation of amines due to the presence of O₂, SO_x and NO_x impurities, is a critical challenge in CO₂ capture units [1,2]. The degradation not only lowers the corrosion resistance and absorption efficiency of the solvent but also generates non-regenerable byproducts, ultimately compromising the sustainability and overall performance of the process [3,4]. The aim of the present study is to assess the impact of MEA degradation on the corrosion characteristics of SS 304L and SS 316L.

2. Experimental / Methodology

Stainless steels 304L and 316L were examined in both degraded and undegraded MEA solutions containing SO_x and NO_x pollutants, under CO₂-loaded and unloaded conditions. Corrosion behavior was evaluated using electrochemical techniques, including potentiodynamic polarization and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy. Microstructural and compositional analyses were carried out with Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) and Energy-Dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) to clarify the underlying corrosion mechanisms.

3. Results and Discussion

The polarization curves of the degraded solutions for both stainless steels were shifted to higher current densities and lower corrosion potentials, while the calculation of corrosion rates indicated a significant increase. These results confirmed that MEA degradation impacts the corrosion performance of the amine system, both in CO₂-loaded and unloaded conditions. These findings were further validated by the lower impedance values observed in the low-frequency region of the Bode plots for the degraded solutions. Also, SS 316L showed better corrosion resistance in CO₂-loaded and unloaded degraded solutions.

Figure 1. [a] Polarization curves of SS 304L and SS 316L in degraded and undegraded MEA solutions, at the temperature of 25°C and [b] calculation of corrosion rates.

4. Conclusions

Amine degradation emerged as a key factor influencing the corrosion performance in CO₂ capture systems. For both stainless steels, exposure to the degraded amine solution resulted in reduced corrosion resistance. However, a comparison between the two alloys revealed that SS 316L exhibited superior corrosion resistance, highlighting its potential as a more durable construction material under such conditions.

5. References

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